

Startup Realization in the Products of Batik Courses, Textile Engineering, Textile Design, and Textile Crafts through *Dudi* in PKK Department, Faculty of Engineering, state University of Semarang

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ABSTRACT :Family Welfare Education (PKK) is an educational institution that prepares graduates of professional education who are experts in technology, including the field of clothing with conservation insight and international reputation. The world of fashion has good prospects for mass development. Thus, these efforts can contribute positively to the development of the creative industry, economic growth, to partners (DUDI), and the community. The potential of the PKK department is very prospective if it is aligned with the Muria Kudus Batik industry. The prospect of this collaboration transforms the PKK FT UNNES Department to develop its products. The advantage of PKK FT UNNES students is that they are able to make batik manually and digitally. In addition, the work of PKK FT UNNES students is supported by various studies. Thus, this collaboration is also expected to make the product known to the public. Through collaboration methods with industry, Batik Muria Kudus has succeeded in developing products and marketing in various segments. One of these efforts is the realization of an independent learning campus that has positive benefits and improves the economy for industry. The production of written batik will be realized through the collaboration of partners and Dikti personnel in the PKK Study Program environment of the Clothing Study Program and within the Dikti personnel environment. The final target of the collaboration is to make the academic community experienced outside the campus with their theoretical abilities. Finally, this collaboration contributes positively to education, tourism, and the creative economy. The method of carrying out this work includes exploration, improvisation, and a broad realization process.

KEYWORDS -StartUp, Batik Course, Work of PKK Department Student, DUDI.

I. INTRODUCTION

Semarang State University (UNNES) is a State University under the Ministry of Research, Technology, and Higher Education (Kemenristekdikti) of the Republic of Indonesia. The purpose of UNNES is to carry out academic and professional education in a number of disciplines, including technology, sports, arts, and culture. As an educational institution, Semarang State University is determined to develop itself into a home for the

development of superior civilization science. Armed with this determination, the State University of Semarang maintains its identity as a scientific institution tasked with developing the potential of human resources in Indonesia to build the nation's excellence and benefits for humans and humanity. Academically, scientific development activities are carried out in Study Programs, Laboratories, and other activities. Non-academic, science becomes the basis in the management and policy-making of the University. Semarang State University as an educational institution strives to continue to carry out national duties in the implementation of education and to develop superior civilizations for the benefit of the Nation, the State, and the World Community. Superior civilization means superior human resources with high-quality values.

Family Welfare Education (PKK) and Fashion Design Education are study programs available at the Department of Family Welfare Education, Faculty of Engineering, Semarang State University. Even though they have a bachelor's degree in education, graduates of Fashion Design Students are not only involved in the teaching and learning process. However, there are various job prospects that can be carried out by graduates of this Department, such as becoming entrepreneurs in the textile sector, designers, and fashion experts. The courses set out in the curriculum include batik, textile engineering, textile design, textile crafts, and fashion design aimed at producing textile products of aesthetic and economic value which are then used as the basis for startup activities. Unfortunately, the products produced from the PKK Department, FT UNNES are still not optimally managed. These works should be used as potential Human Resources that can be developed in collaboration with industrial partners (DUDI) to produce creative and innovative products. The partner who can be invited to collaborate on this program is Batik Muria Kudus because this partner is considered suitable for the proposed program.

Mitra Batik Muria Kudus was founded on September 15, 2005 by Yuli Astuti. Starting from Yuli's limited knowledge of the process of batik, she is active in enriching batik knowledge from the original places where batik comes from, namely from the Pekalongan, Solo, and Yogyakarta areas. Her efforts to learn to make batik led Mrs. Yuli to become a successful young entrepreneur. The resulting batik is written batik and stamped batik with the characteristics of the original Kudus batik. Batik Muria Kudus is one of the home industries in Karang Malang Village, Gebog District, Kudus Regency. The marketing of Muria Kudus batik has a very wide scope to overseas. Mrs. Yuli as the owner of Batik Muria Kudus is currently one of the founders of the Association of Indonesian Batik Craftsmen and Entrepreneurs (APPBI). Mrs. Yuli also joined HIPMI (Indonesian Young Entrepreneurs Association) and BAKUL (Batik Kudus Lovers). In every effort she does, Yuli's mother only wants Indonesia's cultural heritage, especially batik, to continue to grow and be preserved. As a woman who is active in various fields of fashion designer and also in the textile sector, Mitra Batik Kudus wants to develop Kudus batik so that it remains sustainable by carrying out activities that can promote Indonesian batik, especially Kudus batik. One of the efforts that can be taken to realize these expectations is through training or community empowerment activities.

The Dikti personnel need DUDI to achieve the proposed program. Through this Matching Fund activity from Kedaireka, DUDI can collaborate with Dikti Personnel to achieve the same goal. The PKK Department as a producer of batik motifs and quality human resources (students and lecturers) in the field of Textiles and Crafts is therefore collaborating with DUDI, namely Muria Batik Kudus which requires designs, batik motifs, and qualified human resources in their fields. DUDI has experience in fields such as the textile product industry and marketing. This is the reason for holding a collaboration where DUDI is expected to be able to accompany the process of forming StartUp products from courses at PKK UNNES to achieve success.

Summarizing the various goals to be achieved, the Semarang State University college and industrial partner Muria Batik Kudus intend to develop and integrate the products resulting from courses in the PKK FT UNNES Department. This collaboration is supported by DUDI's plan to develop local batik and preserve it. The application of batik motifs needed by partners will be realized in the form of clothing, considering that the departments and study programs at the faculty are the parties that will accommodate and facilitate the manufacture of clothing. Strengthening the Batik Research Center will also be carried out with DUDI/partners in the PKK Department, FT UNNES.

This collaboration has a positive impact on both parties. The Kedai Reka program was also found to be able to create learning opportunities outside campus, both for lecturers and students, develop soft skills and hard skills for campus academics, create references for lecturer research, thesis, or student research and help create job opportunities for graduate students who are directly or indirectly involved. direct. Jobs in tourism and creative economy, as well as study programs, are provisions to maintain the current accreditation status of the University. This effort will also optimize accreditation that does not yet have A status. The collaboration program will become a reference for lecturers to optimize research programs every year. Through the positive impact of cooperation in the Kedai Reka, there will be many benefits in terms of economy, education, tourism, social, and community which will make this program feasible to continue to the next stage so that the program objectives will be carried out optimally.

II. METHOD

Implementation Stage

The collaboration in this shop aims to realize StartUp products for batik courses, textile engineering, textile design, textile crafts, and fashion design through trading businesses by maximizing online/digital 4.0 marketing. The startUp is targeted for business opportunities for the PKK UNNES Department, especially lecturers and students or alumni as jobs and also an inspiration to open new businesses or StartUps according to the fields that students like. StartUp business must be run optimally which therefore requires cooperation with DUDI. DUDI in this case is Muria Batik as a more senior batik textile business actor in the world of batik production and marketing. The choice of StartUp business from PKK UNNES course products provides various benefits, including the following:

- a) A startUp does not require a location that is too strategic. The location of the StartUp business does not require a special place such as an offline store, usually, only a product warehouse due to digital business capital, for this StartUp, uses the product gallery in DUDI with minor repairs/renovations to make it look more attractive. Websites and product gallery videos will also be used to inspire consumers to be interested in visiting the website/product gallery.
- b) StartUp business has a wider market. The consumer market in the StartUp business will be wider because it uses digital marketing, online marketing, and the like that adapts to the current digital 4.0 era. The StartUp market reaches all walks of life where consumers range from young to old, low-high economy, male and female, national-international, and others.
- c) Relatively lower capital. Because capital tends to be low, opening an offline store/conventional business is not necessary considering that it will only require very high funds. That way, the existing capital can be optimized for the product.
- d) Knowledge to build StartUp can be found anywhere. Starting a StartUp business does not have to have a background majoring in business/economics / the like. Anyone with any educational background can get started. PKK UNNES creates StartUp opportunities from products produced by students in the PKK course by inviting the community majoring in PKK to contribute to it, such as lecturers and students. They are invited to build a business and practice being an entrepreneur in the digital era through the establishment of this StartUp. This startup was built in collaboration with DUDI, which has long experience in the batik business.

One StartUp is targeted to be built in early 2021 as a driver for StartUps in the following years. The type of StartUp that wanted to be built in this case is a business in the textile sector where the products sold are the results of batik courses, textile engineering, textile design, textile crafts, and fashion design in the form of batik cloth, batik clothing, batik crafts, handicrafts. craft and others. All of these products are marketed using digital marketing as was done in the 4.0 era with the help of IT experts. IT experts in this case are alumni of UNNES. All students who take StartUp product production courses become team members. The organizational structure is arranged according to the results of the discussion. On the other hand, the Covid-19 pandemic has accelerated digitization in various sectors in Indonesia and even the world. This makes the StartUp business have a good and promising opportunity.

Currently, PKK is in the stage of preparing products that are the result of courses which will then be used as StartUps. In addition to these products, products that were produced together with DUDI will also be sold. The target to be achieved is profit/profit in the form of funds as well as new knowledge, experience, and new jobs. In 2021, the pilot period in 2022 is expected to have a real impact on Dikti and DUDI personnel, such as in the form of stable and increasing profit funds, knowledge, increased student/lecturer experience, and motivation/opportunities for graduates who are later expected to be able to make StartUps. according to the field.

The steps for implementing the StartUp course products for batik, textile engineering, textile design, textile crafts, and fashion design are as follows:

- a) Starting with the DUDI problem that requires batik motif designs by experts as well as the need for human resources in the batik field, which includes academics such as lecturers and students. In addition, a batik research center is also needed. The problem is that PKK UNNES wants to make StartUps from student products in certain courses so that business/business opportunities can be created and motivation for students and lecturers. Research Study Batik also needs to be developed. This background underlies the collaboration in the Kedai Reka Matching Fund program for both parties.
- b) Innovate on various products from PKK courses and DUDI batik products, ranging from stamped/written batik to types of fabric products, clothing, handicrafts, and many more. In addition to preparing products to be marketed, starting from the procurement of batik tools and materials, supporting batik and clothing production, labor, comparative studies were carried out for other motivations/views, the IT team and other members also prepared technology, websites, e-commerce, and other startup needs.
- c) The process of preparing StartUp products apart from student products is a product from DUDI which is made through the design/motif stages by art lecturers/ fine arts students with the theme of regional local wisdom. The products made are then handed over to Muria Batik to be made into written or stamped batik and some will be made into clothing and crafts. The batik concept created by lecturers and students will be made in the form of clothing at Muria Batik by batik artisans and tailors who are employees. Some of the workers at Muria Batik are also interns/PKL students from UNNES who are none other than members of the kedaireka.
- d) After the products and technology are ready, the next step is to realize or run a StartUp of PKK course products with Muria Batik Kudus in the digital era 4.0 with marketing through websites, e-commerce, and others. Not only that, the collaboration between DUDI and PKK was also carried out to strengthen and develop the batik research center in the PKK department of FT UNNES.
- e) When StartUp has started operating, the next action is to prepare for optimizing the facilities and infrastructure of the batik research center laboratory by improving the conditions of space, tools, materials, and other equipment to support the research center in accordance with the DUDI and UNNES Cooperation planning. Not only is the research center optimized, the Muria Batik Kudus product gallery is also renovated to make it look more attractive.
- f) The next stage is to strengthen the research center with experts in the field of batik and provide innovations for the development of the batik research center. DUDI in collaboration with PKK held a written batik training for the general public/communities around Muria Batik Kudus. This is because the location of the training is at DUDI with a limited number of participants, which is around 10-20 participants, and is accompanied directly by PKK lecturers and Mrs. Yuli as the owner of Muria Batik as well as the motivator of Kudus batik.
- g) The StartUp review will be carried out repeatedly so that the StartUp business runs smoothly and generates profits for all collaborating parties. A review is also carried out on the development of a batik research center which will always be monitored and evaluated so that it remains optimal in its management.

Contribution to 8 IKU

Each member in the program of activities has their own task based on their area of expertise. The chairperson of this program is a doctorate who teaches in the department of family welfare education with a secretary from the language and arts faculty and the treasurer from the economics faculty. The suitability of members with their field of expertise will contribute to the expected 8 KPIs. As Dikti Personnel who teach the Department of Family Welfare Education, the Family Welfare Education study program has an important role in producing graduates who are competent and have noble character. The reason is that graduates of the Family Welfare Education study program will later work in several sectors, especially the education sector. Alumni are expected to become professional educators and have superior competence. In the field of skills, students have expertise in several fields such as the arts and fashion as a provision for entrepreneurship and creating jobs. That way, alumni will improve the economy in order to face the era of globalization. In the process of developing soft skills, students also participate in various activities both inside and outside the campus. On-campus, students can join organizations according to their interests and talents. Off-campus, students can participate in research activities proposed by lecturers so that students can hone social skills. This activity is also a manifestation of the implementation of one of the pillars of the Tridharma of Higher Education, namely community service. The basis of efforts to realize the three Tridharma Pillars of Higher Education under the Ministry of Education and Culture is the vision of the Merdeka Campus where Kedaireka realizes convenience in synergizing the contribution of universities with industrial commercialization for the progress of the Indonesian nation. Collaboration or cooperation is needed between the education sector and the industrial sector in creating an invention so that it can increase production and distribution in the domestic and global sectors. The role of the education sector, especially universities, is as a research and development center for the industry to develop new technologies. This Kedaireka is carried out as a means of informing the public about the existence of a platform that can bridge between scientists/academics/students with industry/business that has been needed so far. It is hoped that the business world and education can go hand in hand and provide mutual benefits. Lecturers who are active outside the campus will find it easier to gain industrial experience by involving industrial partners and the wider community. Efforts to support the unification of the mission of the shop can be started by conducting research and field observations to develop and overcome problems from the DUDI side. The results of these observations are studied and processed so that a source of ideas for creating batik motifs is found from local wisdom. Armed with the capabilities possessed by lecturers and students as well as experience and track records that have been passed, DUDI personnel and people collaborate to realize a proposed startup program that will be initiated based on the expertise of each team member and the competence of Muria Batik's partners. This is because the quality of the products produced by students is not optimal due to limitations and constraints. For this reason, it is hoped that the proposed collaboration program of this Kedaireka will help overcome these obstacles and can be used as a means to share knowledge and improve product quality, both in terms of production, economy, and market segmentation. The proposed program for this joint venture focuses on a study center for the creation of batik motifs that are based on the idea of local cultural wisdom where the design is made manually or digitally. The development of the creation of batik motifs is not only supported by the capabilities of partners and the team of higher education personnel but it is also supported by the geographical location of the Semarang State University campus which upholds conservation and cultural values in the local area. StartUp in its proposal focuses on product development that continues to hone creative abilities in order to meet market demand. The hope from the creation of this StartUp is to be able to compete in the global market through the digital world and the modern market.

III. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

Report of Activity Implementation

1. Coordination of Member Lecturers

Implementation: September 5, 2021. Results: Implementation of student membership based on study programs and budget revisions based on approved funds. Obstacles: In the final semester, students who are doing their thesis do not allow MBKM. Many funds must be adjusted based on the approved budget. Completion plan: Final students will be used as surveyors and partly replaced with third and fifth semesters for the realization of the MBKM program and Prepare a revised budget according to the approved one.

2. Coordination with Partners

Implementation: September 10, 2021. Results: Meeting for the preparation of program steps in accordance with the proposal. Constraints: Implementation remains with the process to anticipate the spread of the COVID-19 virus. Completion plan: Implemented by implementing the process without compromising the substance, orientation, objectives, program in accordance with the proposal.

3. Product Photoshoots

Implementation: September 16, 2021. Results: Photoshoots for student products. Constraints: Many student products have to be photographed. Completion plan: Members and a team of photographers take detailed and thorough photo shoots so that no product is missed or doubled in product shooting.

4. Product Identification

Implementation: September 17, 2021. Results: Taking pictures of each product based on the results of the course product, semester, as well as the name of the student per product. Obstacles: Tracing the work of the previous semester, practical problems for the current semester's products in the courses that are included in the kedaireka program. Completion plan: The creation of the work is still carried out with a strict process without compromising the quality and quantity of the work/product.

5. Preparation of Product identification to be uploaded in the E-Commerce System

Implementation: September 20, 2021. Results: Identification of student products is adjusted to the idea of the source of creation and the courses included in the kedaireka program. Obstacles: Student products are presented randomly and must be identified based on qualifications. Completion plan: Designing qualification standards to make it easier to identify products.

6. Creating an E-Commerce account in the Realization of StartUp Products through Social Media such as Facebook Business, Twitter, and Instagram

Implementation: October 04, 2021. Results: E-commerce for the realization of batik kedaireka startup in social media accounts, such as business Facebook, Twitter, and Instagram. Obstacles: There are technical obstacles and the startup process so that student products can be known by the public. Completion plan: Study the policies available on social media such as business Facebook, Twitter and Instagram then upload student products. Here's the link to access their social media accounts:

FACEBOOK <https://www.facebook.com/profile.php?id=100073330001501>

TWITTER <https://twitter.com/startupbatikK>

INSTAGRAM https://www.instagram.com/startup_batikk_r_unnes/

7. Creating E-Commerce Accounts in Realizing StartUp Products on Youtube and Tiktok Applications

Implementation: 08 October 2021. Results: E-commerce for the realization of batik kedaireka startup in Tiktok and YouTube social media accounts. Obstacles: Technical obstacles in the startup process so that student products can be known by the general public. Solution: Study the policies available on social media TikTok and youtube then upload student products. Here's the link for access to the social media account.

TIKTOK <https://vt.tiktok.com/ZSe8rno3K/>

YOUTUBE https://youtube.com/channel/UCz_xEv7Np_mBBXSLJzL59IGw

8. Meeting and Coordination with Students

Implementation: October 10, 2021. Results: Creating E-Commerce for the realization of batik kedaireka StartUp. Obstacles: Difficulty in making E-Commerce International. Solution: Members and team study the step-by-step process for the E-Commerce creation process.

9. Coordination with DUDI Mitra Batik Kudus

Implementation: 20 October 2021. Result: Coordination with DUDI Muria Batik Kudus. Obstacles: Members and teams learn a step-by-step process for the e-commerce creation process. Solution: Coordination with DUDI Muria Batik Kudus regarding batik training activities.

10. Creating E-Commerce Accounts in Product Realization on Market Places, such as Alibaba, Amazon, Blibli, eBay, Etsy, Bukalapak, Lazada, Shopee, and Tokopedia

Implementation: October 08, 2021. Results: The realization of the batik kedaireka startup in social media accounts, such as: Alibaba, Amazon, Blibli, Bukalapak, Ebay, Etsy, Lazada, Shopee and Tokopedia. Obstacles: There are technical obstacles and the startup process so that student products can be known by the general public. Solution: Study the policies available in the marketplace, such as Alibaba, Amazon, Blibli, Bukalapak, eBay, Etsy, Lazada, Shopee, and Tokopedia then upload student products.

ALIBABA https://profile.alibaba.com/profile/my_profile.htm?spm=a2700.7756200.0.0.7bd81afaKxsRKF&tracelog=buyerMaHome

SHOPEE <https://shopee.co.id/user/account/profile>

TOKOPEDIA <https://www.tokopedia.com/batikkrftunnes>

11. Coordination Meeting for Batik Training at DUDI via Zoom Meeting

Implementation: October 26, 2021. Results: Coordination of members for batik training at DUDI Muria Batik Kudus. Obstacles: During the meeting via zoom, there were unfavorable weather conditions in some areas so that the network was unstable. Solution: Members and team coordination to participate in batik training activities at DUDI Muria Batik Kudus.

12. Implementation of the First Day of Batik Training at DUDI Muria Batik Kudus

Implementation: 01 November 2021. Results of the activity: Introduction of tools and materials in batik, followed by training on painting batik. Obstacles: The village head cannot come because there is a sudden need. Solution: Speech on the opening of batik training activities by lecturers, Presentation of material by lecturers and owners of Muria Batik, Members and trainees participating in batik activities while still complying with health protocols, Assistance and taking pictures of activities, Interviews, or interviews with print media journalists.

13. Implementation of the Second Day of Batik Training at DUDI Muria Batik Kudus

Implementation: 02 November 2021. Result: Continuing the batik painting and finishing activities. Obstacles: Some of the training participants were unable to attend due to an urgent need so that the training participants were incomplete. Solution: Continuing the batik painting activity, finishing, closing, and taking photos with the training members together with the results of batik painting.

14. Media Coverage Results

Implementation: 03 November 2021. Results: Media coverage of batik training activities covered by mass media such as Limapagi.id, Lingkar Jateng, Betanews.id and Simpang 5 TV. Obstacles: Constrained by rain which results in not being optimal in the implementation of coverage. Solution: Uploading on mass media, such as youtube channels and other social media.

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=P_Pp47yxFJw/ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=tzk7dvzUDBY>

15. Batik Artwork Copyright Registration

Implementation: November 5, 2021. Results: Registration of copyright for a batik artwork with the title Stork Expression is waiting for approval from DJKI Kemenkumham RI. Obstacles: Online rights registration is waiting for approval from DJKI Kemenkumham RI a little longer. Solution: Waiting for approval from DJKI Kemenkumham RI by following up on the LP2M section.

16. Kedaireka Startup Website

Implementation: November 09, 2021. The website has been completed and can be used. Obstacles: Some members still don't know the application system, so there needs to be an explanation about the introduction of the website system. Solution: As a medium for buying and selling transaction media from the product from the Kedaireka program. Here's the link to access the website: <https://batikkedaireka.id/id>

17. Batik Artwork Copyright Registration

Implementation: November 10, 2021. Results: Registration of copyright for batik artwork with the title Brave Women, is waiting for approval from DJKI Kemenkumham RI. Obstacles: Online rights registration

is waiting for approval from DJKI Kemenkumham RI a little longer. Solution: Waiting for approval from DJKI Kemenkumham RI by following up to LP2M division.

18. Copyright Registration of Batik and General Art Works

Implementation: November 11, 2021. Results: Registration of copyright for batik artwork with the title Sea Eagle Expression and general art with the title Snare dreams are waiting for approval from DJKI Kemenkumham RI. Obstacles: Online rights registration is waiting for approval from DJKI Kemenkumham RI a little longer. Solution: Waiting for approval from DJKI Kemenkumham RI by following up with LP2M division.

19. Research Center

Implementation: November 12, 2021. Results of the implementation of activities: Optimization of the Research Center implementation site. Obstacles: Inadequate facilities and infrastructure when implementing optimization activities. Solution: Completing the preparation of the research center, launching the logo and research center.

20. Partners/DUDI (Muria Batik Kudus) teach in Batik Course

Implementation: November 13, 2021. Results: Provision of material in the batik course on the development of batik motifs by batik industry players as well as their partners. Obstacles: Participants are less

responsive during implementation, so activities run less effectively. Solution: Providing materials by batik industry players as well as their shop partners, Providing understanding about the research center.

21. Batik StartUp Application

Implementation: November 14, 2021. Results: The application has been completed and can be used on Android-based phones. Obstacles: Some members still do not know the application system, so it is necessary to explain the introduction of the application system. Solution: As a medium for buying and selling transaction media from the product from the Kedaireka program.

22. Syncing and Entering Website Addresses to Social Media and E-Commerce Accounts

Implementation: November 15, 2021. Results: Successfully syncing and entering website addresses to social media and e-commerce accounts. Obstacles: Bad weather results in a less supportive signal in the activities. Solution: Promotional events and introduction of the startup's products to a wider audience through Twitter's social media accounts, Facebook Bisnis, Instagram, and Youtube.

IV. CONCLUSION

Based on the Kedaireka program in a study entitled "StartUp Realization of Batik, Textile Engineering, Textile Design and Textile Craft Course Products in the PKK FT UNNES Department with DUDI", several work programs have been carried out which include:

- 1) Coordination of member lecturers
- 2) Coordination with partners
- 3) Product shoot
- 4) Product identification
- 5) Preparation of product identification to be uploaded in the E-Commerce system
- 6) E-Commerce account creation in the realization of startup products: business Facebook, Twitter&Instagram

- 7) E-Commerce account creation in the realization of Youtube and TikTok startup products
- 8). Meetings and coordination with students
- 9) Coordination with DUDI Muria Batik Kudus
- 10) E-Commerce account registration in product realization in E-Commerce
- 11) Coordination meeting for batik training at DUDI via zoom
- 12) Implementation of the first day of batik training at DUDI Muria Batik Kudus
- 13). Implementation of the second day of batik training at DUDI Muria Batik Kudus
- 14) Results of media coverage
- 15) Registration of copyright for batik art
- 16) Creation of a Kedaireka Startup website
- 17) Batik art copyright registration
- 18) Registration of copyrights for batik and general art
- 19) Research center
- 20) Partners/DUDI (Muria Batik Kudus) teaches at batik courses
- 21) Making the Kedaireka StartUp application, and
- 22) Synchronizing and entering website addresses to social media and E-Commerce accounts.